

Original Research Report

Culinary Arts: A Motivator Towards Community-Based Festival Attendance and Sustainability

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Abstract: This study investigates motive factors attracting people to community-based festivals characterized by culinary activities and underscore its contribution to sustaining tourism activities in the study area. Multistage sampling technique was adopted for sample selection. Kayo-Kayo Festival in the Epe area of Lagos State was purposively selected, purposive and availability sampling technique was used to select household head and one additional adult from 25 households respectively within the host community. Convenience sampling method was further used to select 100 festivals attendees, making a total of 150 respondents and a structured close-ended questionnaire was administered for data gathering. Analysis was done through the use of simple percentages, weighted mean, standard deviation and correlation analysis. Majority (79.3%) of the respondents were attracted to community-based festival because of their interest in supporting preservation of cultural heritage (M=2.63; SD=0.85). 48.6% were highly attracted by Culinary arts competition during the festival activities (M=2.41; SD=0.87). Also, most respondents opines that the festival has positive effects on the socio-cultural (M=2.45; SD=1.33) economy (M=2.43; SD= 1.49) and environment (M=3.35; SD=132) of the host community. The study found that there is a positive correlation ($r= 0.356$) between culinary arts and factors that motivate festival attendance. The study concludes that culinary arts motivates peoples' attendance at festivals and therefore recommends sustaining the inclusion of culinary activities in other community-based festivals to promote attendance for the progress of the festivals and its sustainability.

Keywords: Community-Based Festivals, Culinary Arts, Motivator, Sustainability

1. Introduction

Festivals are unique aspect of culture which exhibits peoples' heritage; it is a celebration that promotes unification and happiness amongst the host community. The utilization of festivals for tourism development has been reported to have implications on the culture, economy and physical environment of host region (Kukoyi, 2021).

Culinary art is the combination of the act of making preparation, cooking, presenting and serving of meals. That is, totality of activities engaged in during the process of preparing, cooking and presenting food in the form of meal. Delicacies served in restaurants, events and other kinds of engagement or establishment that includes food services are simply product of culinary arts; and this requires knowledge of the menu recipe and procedure for cooking it, skill for table laying and serving the meal. This practice is found in a competitive manner to form basis of some festivals. It is in view of this that this study investigates the connection between culinary arts and attendance at community-based traditional festivals.

Food is unequivocally vital and critical to human existence and survival on earth; without food, there cannot be life. Food consumed and its modes of preparation are equally a significant aspect of peoples' culture. Some cultural settings even prioritize celebrating certain delicacies that are uniquely attributed to them either by being the originator of such delicacy or being known to place much value on the use of such delicacy for symbolic or festive celebration in their community. Examples of such are: *Ikokore* attributable to Ijebu people, *Ebiripo* attributable to Remo people, *Isapa* soup served with *Iyan* (pounded yam) attributable to Ekiti, Ondo and Ijesha people, *Amala-Lafun* attributable to the Egba people, *Tuwo-Masara* and *Tuwo Shinkafa* attributable to the Hausa people, *Abacha* (an indigenous vegetable salad) attributable to the Igbo people, to mention a few. Serving of these native delicacies at community events most times are major sources of attraction that attracts community indigenes and visitors to the events. The processes involved from preparation to presentation of a cuisine is referred to as culinary art and this may vary from one cultural setting to the other even when preparing the same meal. This greatly influences the culture of a people and in most cases manifest in their festivals and other forms of celebration. Earlier studies have reported that festivals are major attractions that can be used to drive tourism and consequently promote socioeconomic development of a community (Kukoyi et al., 2015 and Kukoyi et al., 2017).

In tourism, food is one of the basic components of a complete tour package and it has been noted to have the capability of serving as an attraction in its own right (Kukoyi, 2022) by serving as the major driving force that attract visitors to a particular destination. Aside from special cuisines that are strategically used as means of attracting customers in fine dining restaurants as reported by Kukoyi et al., (2022). Culinary arts have also been used as major point of attraction to motivate tourists to

festival events. Example of such are; Lagos Food Festivals, which brings together fun lovers and foodies to exhibit varieties of delicacies and drinks from various food vendors and chef across Africa (Oluseyi, 2022). Another example is the Nigerian Food Festivals which holds in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja annually. This festival celebrates local flavours, locally made drinks, veganism and street foods on the foodie calendars. The festival promotes food cooking competition to showcase the rich culinary diversity of Nigeria cuisines and delicacies with the goal of promoting tourism in Nigeria (Omolola, 2018). Also, we have the *Kayo-Kayo* Festival which is a week-long festival celebrated annually by the people of Epe town in Lagos State on the 10th day (Yaom'Al-Ashura) of the first Islamic calendar month (Muharram), which is about one month after the Eid'El-Kabir Festival (Olawale, 2017). *Kayo-Kayo* in the local parlance of the Epe People literarily means “branch and be fed” or “eating to satisfaction”. The *Kayo-Kayo* Festival which began in 1851 showcases the best of the Epe culture, during this festival, there is an exhibition of various local foods alongside display of fashion and other cultural elements (Olatunji, 2019). The festival features cooking competition amongst interested festival participants. *Kayo-Kayo* festival has been acclaimed to be a genuine platform for promoting the cultural heritage of the people and socio-economic development of the host community (Fasogbon, 2021).

Aside from the three examples mentioned above, there some other community-based festivals in Ogun State, Nigeria that showcases culinary art as major highlight of their festival activities. Examples are Ago-Iwoye Day Festival in Ago-Iwoye which promotes *Ebiripo* Night, where a delicacy made from cocoyam is served. Adokun Day Festival in Igan-Okoto which promotes *Okoto* Night, where a delicacy made from snail is served. Owu Day Festival otherwise known as *Odun Omo Olowu* in Abeokuta which promotes celebration of new yam through the symbolic ‘*ela-isu*’ (cutting of new yam) and sliced yam passed round attendees at the festival to share (Adefaka, 2013). Recently, in December, 2022, Iwopin town in Ogun State also had the maiden edition of Ogun Waterside seafood festival. The seafood festival is expected to be an annual event targeted at promoting economic development of Ogun Waterside Local Government Area and expanding the tourism and economic potentials of Ogun State (Henry, 2022). The Ogun waterside seafood festival showcases seafood cuisines and delicacies native to the host communities thereby promoting indigenous knowledge, cultural traditions and advancing tourism in the area. Through this, empowerment of local entrepreneurs is achieved by making the Ogun Waterside area a destination of choice for tourism, culture and economic advancement.

As laudable as the existence of these culinary-based festivals mentioned above may be, there is no empirical evidence of the contribution of many of these food-based festivals in Nigeria reported in academic literature. This research therefore, focuses on the study of *Kayo-Kayo* festival, which is an age-longed community-based festival that showcases culinary activities as major highlight of its celebration with a view to underscore the extent at which culinary activities motivates participants to the festival events and its contribution to sustainability of tourism in the community.

1.1. Statement of Problem

According to (Duxbury and Jeannotte, 2011), culture and sustainability fits together in a variety of settings. Culture facilitates the creation of sustainable communities and its awareness nurtures sustainability (Jiwane, 2015). This makes festival an attractive option to meet the need for economic diversification of a nation (Serkan and Mehmet, 2013). Meanwhile, in recent times most people are skeptical to attend community based traditional festivals as a result of factors such as religion, colonization, migration to mention a few. Most of the traditional festivals however, have potentials to promote socioeconomic development in the rural areas if properly harnessed for tourism purposes. This according to Duxbury *et al*, (2012) will ensure sustainable development growth in the three dimensions of sustainable development (environmental balance, economic growth and social inclusion).

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to examine the level at which festivals attendees are motivated by culinary arts, aspects of the culinary activities that interest them and the effect of culinary-based festival of their host community. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) Identify factors that attract people to attend Kayo-Kayo festival.
- (b) Determine the extent at which culinary activities attract visitors to Kayo-Kayo festival.
- (c) Determine the relationship between culinary arts and interest in festival attendance.
- (d) Investigate the effects of Kayo-Kayo festival on the host community

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) Identify factors that attract people to attend Kayo-Kayo festival.
- (b) Determine the extent at which culinary activities attract visitors to Kayo-Kayo festival.
- (c) Determine the relationship between culinary arts and interest in festival attendance.
- (d) Investigate the effects of Kayo-Kayo festival on the host community

1.4. Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between culinary activities and factors that motivates people to attend community-based festival

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study adopted quantitative survey method as research design and multistage sampling method was utilized to draw sample size for the study.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

All respondents used for data gathering were briefed about aim of the study in order to get their consent for inclusion in data collection.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study area is Epe community of Lagos State, it is a traditional settlement of the Ijebu people of Yoruba tribe. Epe community was founded in the mid 18th century and it is a Local Government Area in the present day Lagos State. Epe is a coastal town located on north side of the Lekki Lagoon and it is well known for its flourishing fish market. Epe town is reported to cover an average of 1,185km² with population of about 181,409 people living there (NPC, 2006).

2.3. Population and Sample

The study population, consisted of adult residents in the study area and attendees of the Kayo-Kayo festival. Purposive sampling method was used in selecting Kayo-Kayo Festival, based on its aged-long existence and reported community-wide involvements in the celebration. Purposive sampling technique was further used to select 25 household heads while availability sampling technique was used to select 1 additional adult from each household making 2 representatives from each household and a total of 50 respondents in the host community. Lastly, convenience sampling technique was adopted to select 100 respondents from the festival attendees due to constraint in time and willingness/readiness of the respondents to participate in the study. This gives a total of 150 respondents all together for the sample size.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A structured close-ended questionnaire was administered to the respondents to elucidate required data on the research subject matter. The questionnaire was given to respective household head and one additional person to fill. Where the household head is a male, the researchers prioritized a female respondent to be the additional person and vice-versa.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Printed questionnaire was handed over to the respondents after been briefed about the research and the respondents are allowed to privately fill in their opinion in the questionnaire. Where respondents find it difficult to comprehend the information in the questionnaire, the researchers assisted in interpreting the content of the questionnaire. All questionnaire were collated after completion for data analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data gathered were subjected to analysis through the use of simple percentages, mean, standard deviation and correlation analysis, while results were presented through the use of tables and notes.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Factors that Attracts People to Attend Community-Based Festival Events

Variables	SD F (%)	D F (%)	A F (%)	SA F (%)	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
I am attracted to the festival because of my interest in supporting the preservation of our cultural heritage.	14 9.3%	17 11.3%	38 25.3%	81 54.0%	Agreed	2.63	0.85	1 st
I am attracted to the festival out of love for fun, merry making and recreation.	08 5.3%	33 22.0%	42 28.0%	67 44.7%	Agreed	2.01	0.83	5 th
I am attracted to the festival because it gives me the opportunity to meet my kinsmen and other childhood friends.	10 6.7%	29 19.3%	43 28.7%	68 45.3%	Agreed	2.23	0.84	2 nd
I am attracted to the festival because of the indigenous cuisines that are prepared and served during the festival events	06 4%	20 13.3%	54 36.0%	70 46.7%	Agreed	2.21	0.80	3 rd
I am attracted to the festival because it gives me the opportunity to socialize with my friends and other community people.	08 5.3%	29 19.3%	37 24.7%	76 50.7%	Agreed	2.05	0.81	4 th

SD: Strongly Disagree; D: Disagree; A: Agree; SA: Strongly Agree; Std. Dev: Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

3.1. Table 1 shows result on factors that attract people to attend community-based festivals, findings from the study revealed that people are attracted to attending community festivals based on several factors. 79.3% agreed that they were attracted to community-based event because of their interest in

supporting the preservation of cultural heritage. 72.7% also agreed that they are attracted to community festival events out of love for fun-seeking, merry-making and relaxation. 74.0% claimed that they get attracted to attending community based festival because it gives them the opportunity to meet their kinsmen and other childhood friends. In addition, majority (82.7%) of the respondents agreed that they are attracted by indigenous cuisines that are prepared and served during the festival events. None the less, 75.4% of the respondents agreed that they are attracted to community-based festivals because it gives them the opportunity to socialize with their friends and other community people. The above result shows confirmation that the motive domains reported by Crompton and Mckay (1997) and Kolabulit and Kilicarslan (2017) remains valid factors that attracts people attend community-based festivals. However, out of the five motive domain considered in this study, cultural exploration (support for preservation of cultural heritage) ranked 1st (M=2.63; SD=0.85), followed by family togetherness (opportunity to meet kinsmen) which ranked 2nd (M=2.23; SD=0.84). This is followed by interest in indigenous cuisines that are prepared and served during the festival events (M=2.21; SD=0.80). This affirms that culinary art is capable of attracting people to attend festival events. This result is in agreement with Kukoyi (2022), that “food can serve as an attraction in its own right” thereby enhancing tourism.

Table 2: Extent which Culinary Activities Attract Visitors to Community-Based Festival Events

Variables	NA F / %	FA F / %	HA F / %	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
To what extent are you attracted to the festival because of culinary activities involved in the festival celebration?	27 18.0%	52 34.7%	71 47.3%	Attracted	1.98	0.91	4 th
To what extent are you attracted to the delicacies served during the festival celebration?	19 12.7%	52 34.7%	79 52.6%	Attracted	2.38	0.81	2 nd
To what extent are you attracted to the art of Meal Preparation during the festival celebration?	27 18.0%	43 28.7%	80 53.3%	Attracted	2.00	0.83	5 th
To what extent are you attracted to the mode of meal presentation and service during the festival celebration?	21 14.0%	57 38.0%	72 48.0%	Attracted	1.93	0.96	3 rd
To what extent are you attracted to the competitive nature of preparation and service of delicacies during the festival	25 16.7%	52 34.7%	73 48.6%	Attracted	2.41	0.87	1 st

NA: Not Attracted; FA: Fairly Attracted; HA: Highly Attracted;

Std. Dev: Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3.2. Table 2 shows result on the extent at which culinary activities attract visitors to Kayo-Kayo festival events. From the table, it can be observed that most the respondents are generally attracted by culinary activities to the festivals. 82.0% of the respondents are attracted to community based festival events because of the culinary activities involved in the festival celebrations. Also, 87.3% were attracted to the delicacies served during the festival celebrations among which 52.6% were highly attracted. In the same vein, 82.0% were attracted to the art of meal preparation while 86.0% were attracted to the mode of meal presentation and service during the festival celebration. In addition, 83.3% of the respondents were equally attracted to the competitive nature of preparation and service of delicacies during the festival. Amongst all the variables in ‘Table 2’, the culinary competition involved in the festivals ranked first (M=2.41; SD=0.87) followed by the delicacies served (M=2.38; SD=0.81) and the mode of meal presentation and service (M=1.93; SD=0.96) as second and third respectively. This implies that the cooking competition which is included in the food-based community festival is what attracts people to the festival mostly, followed by the kind of delicacy that is being prepared. These two things are therefore key motivators in using culinary art to attract people to festival events. These are pointers to the fact that culinary activities in the festival can aid socio-cultural sustainability of the communities through their festivals. This further underscores the position of Dickmen (2012), that festival organizers should know factors that motivate visitors in order to understand how to satisfy them and earn their repeat visit. Therefore, Kayo-Kayo Festival organizers should pay more attention to culinary competition in the festival in order to enhance its sustainability.

Table 3: The Effects of Food-Based Festivals on their Host Communities

Variables	SD F / %	D F / %	A F / %	SA F / %	Remark	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
Sociocultural Effects								
Culinary activities have become inseparable from the activities that characterize your festival.	4 2.7%	6 4.0%	56 37.3%	84 56%	Agreed	1.98	1.37	4 th
Culinary activities in the festivals attracts visitors that are non-indigenes/residents of the community to attend the festival	6 4.0%	5 3.3%	56 37.3%	83 55.3%	Agreed	2.01	1.36	3 rd
Culinary activities make the festival fun filling and interesting to participants.	7 4.7%	9 6.0%	37 24.7%	97 64.6%	Agreed	2.38	1.33	2 nd
Culinary activities in the festival promotes the cultural heritage of the community	4 2.7%	17 11.3%	31 20.7%	98 65.3%	Agreed	2.45	1.33	1 st

Economic Effects									
Culinary activities in the festival aids in attracting sponsors to promote the festival.	7	14	45	84	Agreed	2.43	1.49	1 st	
	4.7%	9.3%	30.0%	56.0%					
Culinary activities in the festival increases chances of economic benefits for traders during the festival	6	15	42	87	Agreed	2.39	1.42	2 nd	Page 201
	4.0%	10.0%	28.0%	58.0%					
Culinary activities in the festival have led to increased revenue generation for local farmers through sales of farm produce in the community during festival season.	4	13	53	80	Agreed	2.27	1.46	3 rd	
	2.7%	8.7%	35.3%	53.3%					
Culinary activities in the festival has led to a huge wastage of money during festival celebration	38	60	44	8	Disagreed	2.21	1.41	4 th	
	25.3%	40.0%	29.3%	5.3%					
Environmental Effects									
Culinary activities during the festival have resulted to increased waste generation which litters the community during the festival.	64	50	14	22	Disagreed	2.13	1.44	4 th	
	42.7%	33.3%	9.3%	14.7%					
Culinary activities during the festivals have resulted into overpopulation in the community during celebration.	42	70	9	29	Disagreed	2.36	1.46	3 rd	
	28.0%	46.7%	6.0%	19.3%					
Culinary activities during the festival have led to increased visitor population in the community which overburdens community's infrastructural facilities.	41	45	23	41	Disagreed	2.67	1.57	2 nd	
	27.3%	30.0%	15.3%	27.3%					
Culinary activities during the festival have resulted into upgrading/facelift of the community infrastructure/amenities.	11	32	42	65	Agreed	3.35	1.32	1 st	
	7.3%	21.3%	28.0%	43.3%					

Key: SD: Strongly Disagree; D: Disagree; A: Agree; SA: Strongly Agree; Std. Dev: Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

3.3. Table 3 reveals the effect of the Kayo-Kayo festival on its host community using the tripods for measuring sustainable development in a community. That is, sociocultural sustainability, economic sustainability and environmental sustainability; result of the sociocultural effects of the festival on its host community shows that 93.3% of the respondents agreed that culinary activities have become inseparable from the activities that characterize their festival. Also, 82.6% agreed that culinary

activities in the festival attract visitors that are non-indigene/residents of the community to attend the festival thereby promoting tourism in the community. 89.3% also agreed that culinary activities make the festival fun-filling and interesting to participants, this corroborates the result of obtained in table 1 which indicated that majority of the respondents were highly attracted by culinary activities to community-based festival events. None the less, 86.0% of the respondents agreed that the culinary activities in their festival promote the cultural heritage of their community. Among the variables under socio-cultural effects of food-based festivals on their host community, “promotion of cultural heritage” ranked 1st (M=2.45; SD=1.33) as the major effect that culinary arts have on their host community. This is followed by “making festival events fun-filling and interesting for participants” which ranked 2nd (M=2.38; SD=1.33). This implies that the inclusion of culinary activities in festival events have the capability of making the event fun-filling, interesting to participants and promoting the cultural heritage of the host community. This is in support of Duxbury *et al.*, (2012), that cultural festivals aids in sustainable development growth by enhancing environmental balance, economic growth and social inclusion.

Table 3 further shows result of the economic effects of Kayo-Kayo festival on the host community. From the table, it can be seen that 83.0% of the respondents agreed that culinary activities in the festival aids in attracting sponsors to promote the festival, 86.0% also agreed that culinary activities in the festival increases chances of economic benefits for traders during the festival. In addition, 88.6% of the respondents agreed that culinary activities in the festival have led to increased revenue generation for local farmers through the sale of farm produce in the community during the festival season. Never the less, 65.3% of the respondents disagreed that culinary activities have led to a huge waste of money during festival celebration. This implies that majority believes that money spent on the culinary activities in the festival is worth with. Among all the variables considered for evaluating economic effects of the festivals on their host communities, the ability of culinary activities in the festival to attract sponsors to promote the festival ranked 1st (M=2.43; SD=1.49) followed by ability of culinary activities in the festival to increase chances of economic benefits for traders and increase revenue generation for local farmers during festival seasons which ranked 2nd (M=2.39; SD=1.42) and 3rd (M=2.27; SD=1.46) respectively. This implies that involving culinary activities during the festival is a good way of ensuring sustainability of the festival since it can attract sponsors to fund the festival activities. Likewise, it is a good way of promoting community sustainability since it helps in improving economic benefits and revenue generation for traders and farmers. This can help in reducing poverty in the host community and enhance economic sustainability. This is in line with the submission of Duxbury *et al.* (2012) and Jiwane (2015), that “culture is a facilitator in creating sustainable communities.

Table 3 lastly shows result of the environmental effect of Kayo-Kayo festival on the host community. From the table, it can be deduced that 76.0% of the respondents disagreed that culinary activities during the festival have resulted into increased waste generation which litters the community during the festival. Also, 74.7% of the respondents disagreed that culinary activities in the festival have

resulted into overpopulation in the community during the festival celebration. 57.3% also disagreed that culinary activities during the festival have led to overburdening of community infrastructural facilities/amenities, while 71.3% agreed that culinary activities during the festivals have resulted into upgrading/facelift of their community infrastructural amenities. Among the variables considered on the environmental effects, ability to bring about upgrading/facelift of community infrastructural facilities ranked 1st (M=3.35; SD=1,32). This implies that the festival planning committee and policy makers in the community prioritize use of the festival as an opportunity to upgrade community infrastructure/amenities. This may have been achieved through proceeds from sponsors or other means as indicated by Kukoyi, (2021) in which the festival generates economic gain for the community. More so, disagreement with the statement that “culinary activities overburden community infrastructural facilities” which ranked 2nd (M=2.67; SD=1.57) equally meant that as at now, the population of people attending the festivals have not outweighed the carrying capacity of the host community. It can therefore be deduced that culinary activities during the festivals have not debar environmental sustainability of the host community. This result is equally in agreement with the findings of Duxbury *et al.*, (2012) that cultural festivals have potential to support sustainable growth in the three dimensions of sustainability, namely; environment balance, economic growth and social inclusion.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing relationship between culinary activities and factors that motivates people to attend community-based festivals.

		Culinary Activities	Motivating factors to attend festivals
Culinary Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	.356**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	150	150
Motivating factors to attend festivals	Pearson Correlation	.356**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	150	150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors (2023)

3.4. Table 4 shows result of hypothesis tested “There is no significant relationship between culinary activities and factors that motivates people to attend community-based festival”. From the table, it can be deduced that there is positive relationship between culinary activities and factors that motivate people to attend community-based festivals based on coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.356$). This implies that motivation to attend community-based festivals can be improved upon if culinary activities are improved upon or even included where it does not exist. Although, the association between culinary activities and factors that motivate people to attend community festival showed a weak positive value

with a correlation coefficient of approximately 35.6%, the probability value of 0.001 indicates that it is significant since it is less than p-value of 0.10 (10%), 0.05 (5%) and 0.01 (1%). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. This implies that a significant relationship exists between culinary activities and factors that motivate people to attend community-based festivals.

4. Conclusion

The outcome of this study has been able to add to literature by reemphasizing the factors reported by Crompton and McKay (1997); Zyl and Botha (2004); Kolabulut and Kilicarslan (2017) to be motivators that attract people to traditional festivals. In addition, the study has also probed into factors that specifically attract people to food-based community festivals and it has been able to find that certain culinary arts specifically motivated visitors to be interested in some food-based community festivals. Amongst the five culinary motive domains considered in this study, majority of the festival attendees were highly attracted to community festival by all. This means the respondents find all act of culinary activities in the festivals attractive. However, the competitive nature of preparation and service of delicacies during the festivals tops all other motive domains in attracting visitors to food-based community festivals. This meant that culinary art is capable of motivating people to attend community-based festival. This study also found that, inclusion of culinary activities in community-based festivals has positive impacts on the host community and it enhances sociocultural, economic and environmental sustainability in the host community. This study submits that culinary art is a motivator towards attending community-based festival and it enhances sustainable community development. On this basis, the study recommended that community-based festival organizers should pay more attention to improving/including culinary activities in festival events planning to better promote their festival for tourism advancement and community development. Partnership with food companies and incorporating digital marketing to the festival events planning for wider reach of potential tourists can help expand attendance at the festival and as well make the festival more beneficial to the host community.

Government and other policy makers are advised to support promotion of indigenous culinary arts which this study has found to aid in motivating tourists to attend community-based festivals thereby preserving our cultural heritage.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors of this article hereby declares no conflict of interest with respect to this article.

Author Contributions

All the authors immensely contributed towards the success of this article. The first author (who is also the corresponding author) played major role in conceptualization of the research and data collection while other authors assisted in data processing and reporting.

Data Availability Statement

Data used for the study is a primary data as obtained by the researchers. It would be made available on request with conditions attached by the researchers.

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